

Smart Traffic System Using Arduino

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Abstract - In this project, we'll use Arduino to create a traffic light controller that is dependent on density. The key message of this paper is that one shouldn't wait for the other light if there won't be any traffic there. The system will go on to the subsequent signal after skipping that one. The primary component of this paper is Arduino, which will be used to read data from an ultrasonic sensor (HC-SR04) and determine distance. This distance will indicate whether or not a vehicle is in close proximity to the signal, and the traffic signals will be managed accordingly. The key task was to avoid using the delay function because we had to continuously read data from the ultrasonic sensors while simultaneously controlling signals, which required the usage of the delay function. To measure time in microseconds repeatedly and execute an interrupt function at the end of each measurement, we used the timer one library. We will read data from the sensors in this function, and we will operate the traffic signals in the loop function.

Keywords – IR; Electricity Generation; Traffic Light; Density based; LED and HC-SR04

1.0 Introduction

Several countries nowadays experience severe traffic congestion issues that have an impact on the city's transportation infrastructure. The optimization of the huge traffic jam is still a significant problem to be confronted, especially with several junction nodes, despite the automatic traffic systems replacing officers and flagmen. The promotion of infrastructure with enough resources is not keeping pace with the quick development in automobiles and the steadily rising number of road users. Road construction, flyover and bypass construction, ring construction and road repair are partial solutions.

Fig.1: Concept of Adaptive Traffic Light Control System

1.1 Aim of the Project

It is feasible to provide dynamic time-based coordination solutions where the green signal time of the traffic lights is allotted based on the current traffic conditions. Every traffic light at an intersection typically has a set amount of time when it is green. In to tackle the problem, we created a framework for a dynamic, automatic traffic light control system as well as a simulation model with embedded algorithms that would aid in the hardware implementation of the system. The project's goal is to address traffic congestion, which is a serious issue in many contemporary cities around the globe. We can stop the needless occurrence of traffic jams that inconvenience the general population. When compared to time-based traffic control, density-based traffic signal control offers significant time savings. The microcontroller in the circuit will flawlessly complete the intelligent task carried out by the traffic inspector with the aid of sensors and the software that is programmed to the microcontroller. At junctions, traffic inspectors are not necessary to supervise the flow of traffic. So, based on the aforementioned theory, we can infer that employing the method of density-based regulation of traffic lights will allow us to save a significant amount of time as well as prevent excessive traffic jams, which would result in a smooth flow of traffic. The time-based control of traffic signals that are now in use in India result in massive traffic jams around the country, which wastes a lot of time and fuel. We hope that these approaches will be used as quickly as feasible to get around the problems our current approach is having.

1.2 Inspiration To Construct This Project

In these days we all know how busy roads are with vehicles. Many times, it has been observed that when many vehicles are stand in a queue waiting for the green signal instead of glow green light on this road, it automatically glows green signal to the other side of roads due to timing system in traffic light where there are no any vehicles is standing in a queue. So, this projects really help every people by saving their time and also it reduces the pollution. IR sensors are employed in this system to calculate the density of the fixed cars within a given distance. All of the sensors are connected to the microprocessor, which regulates the traffic signal system based on the density that the sensors detect. More priority is given the side if the traffic density is strong there. The sensors continuously monitor the density on both sides, and the side that the sensors identify as having a high density is given the green signal first. Following the first priority level is the side with the next priority level. By utilizing this approach, delays even when there is no traffic on the opposite side may be avoided and traffic can be cleared without any anomalies.

1.3 Principle of Project

The microcontroller is the main component of this traffic system. Traffic lights are attached to PORT B and PORT D, while IR sensors are connected to PORT C (PC0, PC1, PC2, and PC3) of the microcontroller. If there is traffic, the sensor's output changes to logic 0; otherwise, it changes to logic 1. We must develop the application to regulate the traffic systems using the outputs from these IR sensors. We must send a green signal to that specific path and a red signal to all other paths if any of these sensors send logic 0 signals. Now, we have to regularly check the IR sensors for traffic.

Fig.2: Density Based Traffic Lights System Circuit Diagram

2.0 Details of Connections

Four infrared sensors, an atmega8 microprocessor, and four traffic lights make up this circuit. An IR transmitter resembles an LED in appearance. This IR transmitter constantly emits IR rays. This IR transmitter's working voltage ranges from 2 to 3 volts. These IR (infra-red) rays are not visible to the naked eye. Yet, a camera can be used to see these infrared light. IR transmitter sends out IR rays, which are picked up by IR receiver. When an IR receiver is receiving IR photons, its resistance, which is typically in the mega-ohm range, is very low. The IR receiver's working voltage ranges from 2 to 3V. These IR pairs must be positioned so that, even with an obstruction in their path, the IR receiver can still receive the IR rays. When we provide power, the IR rays that are being transmitted strike the item and bounce back to the IR receiver. Use LEDs in place of traffic lights (RED, GREEN, YELLOW). You need to glow the LEDs on schedule in a typical traffic system. If there is a lot of traffic on any one path, both the green LED for that path and the red LEDs for the other paths will glow. In a typical traffic system, we give each path a one-minute grace period. Paper preparation instructions must be adhered to precisely.

2.1 Circuit Diagram of IR Sensor Circuit.

Fig.3: IR Sensor Circuit

2.2 Components Requirements & Details:

Circuit Components for Density Traffic System:

- Printing Circuit Board
- Infrared sensors -4
- Light Emitting Diodes-12(4-red,4-green,4-yellow)
- 12v Battery or adaptor
- Serial cable
- Connecting wires
- LDR
- Resistor
- Motor

Fig. 4: Components after Testing.

3.0 Methodologies & Construction

- Connect 12V battery or adaptor to the development board.
- Switch on the supply.
- Burn the program to the ATmega8 microcontroller by keeping the programming switch sw2 in program mode.
- Connect four IR sensors to PORT C.
- Connect LEDs to PORT B and PORT D.
- Arrange all this LED's same as like traffic lights.
- Arrange one IR sensor for each road.
- Now you can see the normal traffic system based on time basis.
- Now if you place any obstacle in front of any IR sensor, then the system allows the traffic of that particular path by glowing GREEN light.
- Finally, turn off the board power supply.

3.1 About our project

Due to the fast growth of automobiles and the long delays between traffic signals, controlling the flow of traffic has become a serious problem in modern times. We shall thus use a system of traffic signals based on density to solve this issue. This article shows how to manage traffic based on density. And also generating electricity with the help of shaft and then we will use this energy as in use of street light. And LDR will be used in this project for the energy saving process.

3.2 Project Construction Steps

A flexible hump made of steel stripes, angles, and channels fitted and hinged together in such a manner in the form of hump, which can be pressed and released vertically down and up supported by springs, is depicted in the mechanical diagram of the electricity generation system by the hump arrangement on the road. At the base of the hump arrangement, a flexible vertical shaft is hinged, and its opposite end is hinged with a crank that is 0.859 metres long and angled at a 45-degree angle to the horizontal. Another 0.070 m diameter fly wheel is positioned and designed to rotate 1.5 revolutions for every crank revolution. After that, the spiral spring was axially attached to the flywheel's shaft. In order to generate the desired amount of power, the spiral spring shaft's unwinding is next connected to the generator's shaft.

4.0 Future layout

We are aware that in the near future, all of the crude oil that has been stored in the ground will be used, and that alternative, environmentally friendly, non-polluting energy sources will be used to generate the electricity needed to power our cars. One of these alternate power sources is the battery. Currently, battery-powered automobiles, scooters, and three-wheelers can be seen on the roadways. Throughout the ensuing years, it is anticipated that the number of such battery-powered vehicles would rise tremendously. By taking into account all the information and calculations, it has been determined that the hump (speed breaker) configuration on roads has a significant potential for power generation. It has been calculated that a line of these small power generating units may produce about 700 kw of power. The idea is to use a hump (similar to a speed breaker) in the road to generate power while also capturing energy from the forces created by a car's wheels as it travels down a road.

4.1 Generation of Electricity

Components Required

- Gear Generator (1000rpm)
- A medium Pipe (for connecting to shaft of the generator)
- Two clips.

4.2 Function

The fundamental function of this part in this project is the generation of electricity without polluting the environment (i.e., clean energy). The basic principle is that a rod or pipe will be placed between the roads just (above the it), and the pipe or rod will be connected to the shaft

of the generator. And when the vehicles will pass across the rod, the rod will rotate, and thus in this way energy will be generated. A gear box will be attached to the generator to give generator a constant speed to generate the required output. The generated energy can be stored in the battery for future use or can be used directly for nearby purposes.

Fig.5: Circuit Diagram of whole part generation of electricity.

4.3 Fabrication of the project

Cost of Components

PCB board (2*100) = 200
 IR sensors - 4 (4*250) = 1000
 LED's-12(4-red, 4-green, 4-yellow) (12*4) = 48
 12v Battery or adaptor (3*20) = 60
 Serial cable (5*15) = 75
 Connecting wires (12*5) = 60
 LDR =60
 Gear Generator (1000rpm) = 440
 Pipe rod = 30

5.2 Cost on Project

Total Cost on this Project around Rs.1973/-
 Rs. ~2000/-

5.0 Conclusion

For traffic control at crossroads crossings, a density-based traffic light control system was developed in this design effort to reduce road traffic fatalities and remove needless time waste, which the current conventional traffic light control system has failed to do. According to test results from the simulation and prototype implementation, the design has demonstrated that the system created is a practical tool for traffic control, and its adoption would help reduce the number of traffic fatalities caused by drivers who disobey traffic signals. The design goals were

ultimately achieved. This study describes a system for controlling traffic at crossroads crossings using infrared sensors with an embedded microprocessor chip. It demonstrates how a useful software application may manage traffic based on how much traffic is using each lane at the crossroads. It provides an alternative to the conventional traffic light, which is linked to consistent scheduling of traffic lanes, independent of that lane's density, or the number of cars per kilometre. By using renewable energy sources to run the device continuously for 24 hours, this idea can be made even more inventive. Additionally, the system might be configured to alert the relevant traffic authorities the acquired vehicle plate numbers of defaulters immediately. The design can also be altered to accommodate more than four lanes of traffic. Because it doesn't use any environmentally harmful components, this process is very beneficial for generating energy. It is a cutting-edge energy production technique.

6.0 Suggestions for Future Work

Future plans for the density traffic light system include regulating the traffic lights in according to the information gathered, as well as profiling the traffic by storing the data. The profiling can also be used to examine traffic patterns and the changes in traffic density over the course of a day, a week, a month, or an entire year. Additionally, we can adapt the system to fit emergency vehicles like ambulances.

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